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wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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Contributors	Nicolas G. Alonso De Linaje, DTU

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract This report describes the WIMBY deliverable D1.1 – Wind resources API. It provides a description of the data relevant for estimating long-term wind resources and siting parameters and time series of wind speed, direction and other meteorological parameters for any European site. This data is used in the Wind Power tool and by other partners in their model development and calculations.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AEP	Annual Energy Production
AGL	Above Ground Level
API	Application Programming Interface
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasting
ERA5	ECMWF reanalysis Version 5
GASP	Global Atlas for Siting Parameters
GWA	Global Wind Atlas
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
NEWA	New European Wind Atlas
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
WRF	Weather, Research and Forecasting

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the meteorological and wind energy data required for the WIMBY Wind Power tool and other partners' model development and calculations for the WIMBY project. Most of the data comes from previous projects but has been enhanced and expanded specifically for use in WIMBY.

The main datasets shared are:

- Wind resource climatologies, provided by the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) and Global Wind Atlas projects;
- Wind resource time-series from the NEWA project;
- A new dataset characterizing the temporal variation of wind speed created using data from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset;
- Turbine classification data based on siting data (e.g., turbulence and extreme winds) from the Global Atlas of Siting Parameters; and
- A database of harmonized wind turbine locations created as part of a project funded in collaboration with the Danish Meteorological Institute.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind resource data encompasses diverse information crucial for assessing the potential for harnessing wind energy. Meteorological data, such as wind speed and direction, provides insights into the prevailing atmospheric conditions. Wind resource data is used in many of the WIMBY applications. Due to their varying requirements and source model errors, each application's data selection varies.

This report describes the relevant meteorological and wind energy data needed for use in the WIMBY Wind Power tool and by other partners in their model development and calculations as part of the WIMBY project. Much of the data comes from existing projects but has been improved and expanded for use in WIMBY. The key data described here are:

- Wind resource climatologies, provided by the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) [1] and Global Wind Atlas projects [2],
- Wind resource time-series from the NEWA project,
- A new dataset characterizing the temporal variation of wind speed created using data from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset [3],
- Turbine classification data based on siting data (e.g., turbulence and extreme winds) from the Global Atlas of Siting Parameters [4], and
- A database of wind turbine locations (and later technical specifications) created as part of a project funded by NCKF, the National Climate Center at the Danish Meteorological Institute.

The remainder of the report is organized as follows: Chapter 2 details the methods used to update the datasets for WIMBY, including additional simulation and changes to the data structures and distribution. Chapter 3 describes the datasets, where they can be accessed, and who can access them. Chapter 4 includes a summary and the additional work that needs to be carried out on the datasets to be used throughout the WIMBY project.

2 METHODS

2.1 Extension of the NEWA time series data

As part of the WIMBY project, the NEWA mesoscale (time series) data was extended from the original period of 1989–2018 to include 2019–2022. The original simulations were carried out in the Barcelona Supercomputer Center cluster (MareNostrum 4) under the funding of a PRACE¹ access allocation. Since the allocation is finished, the new WRF [5] model simulations were done using the Sophia cluster at DTU.

The new simulations used the exact same model version and configuration as those for the earlier period. But, because of differences in the compilation of the WRF model executable, the runs at MareNostrum4 and Sophia are not bit by bit identical. However, the wind climatologies are consistent.

The raw output from the WRF model was post-processed using the same Python scripts as used in the NEWA project, with one exception. The original scripts had a bug in handling the solar data; this bug was fixed as part of the updated simulations. This means that correct solar data will now be part of the NEWA project. The post-processing extracts and pre-computes variables of interest for the Wind Energy community and interpolates variables to seven desired heights AGL (see Table 2.1). This reduces the size of the dataset while making it easy to use in wind energy projects.

2.2 Updating NEWA time series Data Storage

The post-processed NEWA time series data is approximately 150 terabytes in size. This makes storing and accessing it a challenge. The data was originally stored as daily netCDF [6] files for all of Europe. While netCDF is a traditional format for scientific data and is favored for its rich data model, it is less efficient with large datasets, has challenges with multiple processes trying to access the same file at the same time, and requires files to be kept relatively small, on the order of a few gigabytes. In recent years, the Zarr [7] format has been developed to help address some of these shortcomings. Zarr can use the same rich data model as netCDF but is designed for cloud and large-scale applications, which makes it better at handling large datasets, such as NEWA. A Zarr archive consists of many files stored in a specific binary format with a specific

¹PRACE: Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe, <https://prace-ri.eu/>

Table 2.1: Details of the NEWA mesoscale wind atlas datasets.

Mesoscale wind atlas	
Property	Description
Horizontal grid spacing	3 km × 3 km
Vertical levels	50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 500 m AGL
Temporal resolution	30 minutes
Period covered	1989–2018 (updated to 2019–2022)
Static fields	Surface elevation Land mask (1 land; 0 ocean) Dominant land use category
Single-level fields	time series of: Boundary layer height Wind speed at 10 m Air temperature at 2 m Air temperature at 100 m Turbulent kinetic energy at 50 m Surface air density surface pressure
Multi-level fields	time series of: Wind speed and direction Wind power density Air temperature Water vapor specific humidity

naming convention and several JSON files to handle the metadata. The small binary files store “chunks” of the larger dataset; a chunk is a multi-dimensional slice of the larger dataset.

As part of the WIMBY project, we converted the netCDF data to Zarr using the following chunk sizes (time=17,520 (365 days); height=1; west_east=50; and south_north=50). This storage approach focused on making the data easier to extract as time series data for a few points. The previous daily-based storage made it easier to extract the entire domain for a single time period. The focus on long-term period extraction was something that had been identified as a preferred access pattern after the NEWA project finished.

During the data conversion, it was discovered that the interpolation func-

Figure 2.1: ERA5-derived wind speed at 100 m averaged over the month of the year and the time of the day for a grid point located at 40°N and 10°E.

tion from the WRF-python package [8], which was used in the post-processing step to interpolate the model levels to heights, added a few random NaN values across the whole dataset. This has slowed the data conversion process slightly and will require some fixes later.

2.3 Creation of time variation dataset

Certain WIMBY models require a description of the time variations of wind speed over time. The complete time series is large, making them slow to obtain and challenging to work with. As an alternative for these models, we developed a so-called 12 (months) × 24 (hours) table of wind speed averages from the ERA5 wind speed for the 10-year period of 2013–2022. An example of this evolution is given in Fig. 2.1 for a grid point located at 40°N and 10°E. This dataset covers all Europe from 15°W–35°E and from 35°N–72°N.

Because of the known biases in wind speed of the ERA5 over complex terrain [1], we suggest that the 12 x 24 mean wind speed is bias corrected before use. The procedure should be as follows. The mean wind speed, \bar{U} , is corrected as

$$\bar{U}(x, y, \text{month}, \text{hour}) = \bar{U}_E(x_E, y_E, \text{month}, \text{hour}) \times w(x, y) \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2.2: Ratio [-] between the mean wind speed from GWA2 and that from ERA5 over Europe at 100 m AGL.

where (x, y) is the turbine location, (x_E, y_E) is the ERA5 grid point closest to the turbine site, and $w(x, y)$ is the GWA-derived bias correction ratio (defined as GWA2 divided by ERA5) at the turbine site. A map of these weights at 100 m is shown in Fig. 2.2. This method has been successfully used in [9, 10], and verified against wind and power observations.

3 DATASET DESCRIPTION

This section provides a description of the different datasets and where they can be obtained.

Name	Description	Location
ws_mean_era5_12_by_24	ERA5 12 x 24 wind speed mean	YODA
bias_correction_era5_ratios	Spatial ratio between the GWA2 wind speed and that of the ERA5	YODA
wind_turbine_database	Harmonized Turbine locations over Europe	YODA
NEWA Microscale Data	Mean wind speed distribution from NEWA ^a	NEWA microscale ^b
NEWA Mesoscale time series	30-min resolution time series data from NEWA ^c	NEWA mesoscale ^d

^aThis is the original NEWA data, without the last four years of WRF simulations or the updated surface roughness treatment. That will be processed before the next deliverable of this report.

^b<https://wps.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/api/microscale-atlas/v1/docs>

^cThis has not been updated to the new Zarr archive, nor to include the last four years of WRF simulations. That will also be done before the next deliverable of this report.

^d<https://wps.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/api/mesoscale-ts/v1/docs>

3.1 Wind resource data

Wind resource data can be represented in different forms depending on the application. High-resolution datasets provide climatological statistics about the wind, including the wind speed and direction distributions over a long period of time. To better understand how the wind speed and direction vary over time, temporal averages are provided via a 24x12 table, which provides the mean wind speed for each hour of each month based on coarser resolution data. Finally, for the best temporal resolution, 30-minute time-series data is provided for the period 1998–2022. The data volume for the time-series data is significantly larger than the other data and, therefore, only used when absolutely necessary.

3.1.1 ERA5 data

The ERA5 dataset [3] is derived from the Copernicus collection of ECMWF reanalysis data [11] – an atmospheric reanalysis of the global climate covering the period from January 1940 to the present. ERA5 combines

vast historical observations into global estimates using advanced modelling and data assimilation systems. Because of data assimilation, ERA5 is a good choice for applications requiring accurate time variations. However, the provided wind data might contain systematic errors, especially over complex terrain [1].

In the WIMBY project, ERA5 data was used to create the “12 x 24 mean wind speed”, described in Section 2.3.

3.1.2 Global wind atlas (GWA2/GWA3) data

The Global Wind Atlas (GWA) is a free, web-based application developed to help policymakers, planners, and investors identify high-wind areas for wind power generation virtually anywhere globally and perform preliminary wind resource calculations [12, 2].

The microscale wind speed data is used to bias correct the ERA5 climatologies and time series. The scaling factor is computed between the long-term mean wind speed from the reanalysis and the mean wind speed from the GWA2. We recommend using the data from the older GWA2 dataset released in November 2017 instead of the newer GWA3 (released November 2018) because of known biases in the microscale downscaling [13, 9]. These biases are also present in the NEWA microscale data, especially over complex terrain. Within the WIMBY project, we plan to re-calculate the NEWA microscale wind atlas using updated surface roughness lengths and generalization procedures, which are believed to cause the biases. An updated correction factor map will be created from that dataset.

3.1.3 NEWA data

The NEWA data is taken from the mesoscale simulations of the New European Wind Atlas [14, 1], a previous project funded by the European Commission (topic FP7-ENERGY.2013.10.1.2) . These simulations were created using the Weather, Research and Forecasting Model, WRF [5]. We also used the microscale layers of the NEWA wind atlas that were created using the WAsP model [15]. Dörenkämper et al. [1] describes the methods and provides validation of the NEWA wind speeds at turbine height against many tall masts in Europe. Further validation was carried out in [13, 10], and the wind speed fields at the sea surface are compared to satellite data in [16].

The WRF model simulations were run using the ERA5 [3] reanalysis. Land surface properties were modified from the standard WRF model simulations carried out in the NEWA project using WRF version 3.8.1 to match European land characteristics [1]. Further details on the NEWA mesoscale database are given in Table 2.1.

Figure 3.1: Long-term mean wind speed (in m s^{-1} for 1989–2018) at 100 m from the NEWA project.

The NEWA simulations were done over ten different domains that share an outer grid and cover all European Union member states, Norway, Turkey, Switzerland, and the Balkans, as well as offshore areas 100 km off each coast and the complete North and Baltic seas (See the NEWA paper [1] Figure 1). The data from these ten domains were combined by selecting a given domain for each country and including data from that domain for all of that country's economic exclusion zone to form a continuous dataset at $3 \text{ km} \times 3 \text{ km}$ spatial grid spacing. Figure 3.1 includes the long-term (1989–2018) mean wind speed; an outline of the original NEWA domains is still identifiable. These identifiable differences in wind speed in the overlap of the computational domains are less than 0.1 m s^{-1} . The simulations also overlap in time during the spin-up period of 24 h, which is discarded, as described in [17]. Time series are extracted directly from these simulations.

For distribution in the WIMBY project, the data has been reorganized in many ways. The processes used for the reorganization are described in Section 2.1.

Table 3.1: Details of the NEWA microscale wind atlas datasets.

Microscale wind atlas	
Property	description
horizontal resolution	50 m × 50 m
vertical levels	50, 100, 200 m AGL
temporal resolution	long-term climatology
period covered	1989–2018 (to be updated to include 2019–2022)
available raw fields	mean air density, frequency f and Weibull parameters for 12 wind direction sectors (0° to 360°) of 60° each.
derived fields	long-term mean of wind speed and wind power density

3.2 Wind siting data

Wind turbines are designed for specific conditions. During the construction and design phase, assumptions are made about the wind climate to which the wind turbines will be exposed.

The Global Atlas for Siting Parameters (GASP) project created a global atlas of siting parameters, including the 50-year wind, turbulence, and turbine class recommendations based on relevant generic turbines, at a spatial resolution of 275 m. More details are given in [4]. Using the correct turbine type helps to lower the risk of over-designing by reducing the critical mismatch between the turbine and the site.

Wind classes determine which turbine is suitable for the normal wind conditions of a particular site. Turbine classes are determined by three parameters: the average wind speed, extreme 50-year gust, and turbulence. Modern wind turbines are typically designed according to the requirements for class certification defined by the IEC 61400-1 design standard, as outlined in Table 3.2. There are three main classes of turbines based on the 50-year wind at a temporal resolution of 10 min at the hub height and the annual average wind speed, each with subclasses based on turbulence. Extreme winds and turbulence statistics are needed to determine what types of turbines can withstand the site-specific wind loads.

Figures 3.2 and 3.3 show two examples from GASP for Europe [source: GWA web site [12]]. The GASP IEC Class for Fatigue loads shows the wind

Table 3.2: Wind turbine design classes in IEC 61400-1 ed 4. Adapted from [4].

Wind turbine class	I	II	III
Annual average wind speed (m s^{-1})	10.0	8.5	7.5
Reference extreme wind speed (m s^{-1}) over 10 min	50.0	42.5	37.5
A+ category for very high turbulence characteristics		0.18	
A category for higher turbulence characteristics		0.16	
B category for medium turbulence characteristics		0.14	
C category for lower turbulence characteristics		0.12	

turbine class in terms of mean wind speed (wind turbine class I, II, III, and S) and turbulence parameters (turbulence category A+, A, B, and C) from Table 3.2. The GASP IEC Class for Extreme loads shows the wind turbine class in terms of extreme wind speed and air density at high wind speed (wind turbine class I, II, III, T and S) from Table 3.2.

3.3 Wind turbine database

As part of a project funded by the National Climate Center at the Danish Meteorological Institute (NCKF), a database of wind turbine locations and technical specifications (hub height, rotor diameter, rated power, thrust, and power curves) was created. The database combines information from national datasets [18, 19, 20], a European-wide wind farm database [21], OpenStreetMap [22] and the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) [23].

Extensive work was carried out to harmonize and gap-fill the combined dataset, including filling missing data via random-forest-based models and associating wind farm information with individual turbines via a developed wind farm splitting algorithm. Figure 3.4 shows a spatial overview of the turbine locations, associated hub heights (H), and rotor diameters (D).

Besides the location of the wind turbines, the database also contains the turbine type, hub height and rotor diameter, rated power, cut-in and cut-out wind speed and the turbine power and thrust curve. The commissioning and decommissioning dates of the wind farms are also part of the database.

The dataset uploaded to YODA includes all European land wind turbines; offshore wind turbine locations are only available in GB, NL, FI, IE, NO, BE, FR, SE, DE, and DK. A count of the number of turbines per country is presented in Table 3.3.

Figure 3.2: GASP IEC Class for Fatigue loads at 100 m.

Figure 3.3: GASP IEC Class for Extreme loads at 100 m.

Figure 3.4: Location of individual wind turbines in the database (dots). The dots are colored by the turbine hub height and scaled by the rotor diameter.

Table 3.3: Number of land-based and offshore wind turbines in the wind turbine dataset per country as of November 2022.

Country	Onshore	Offshore	Country	Onshore	Offshore
AT	983	-	BE	821	401
BY	12	-	CH	36	-
CZ	178	-	DE	26,656	1,499
DK	4,775	604	EE	123	-
FI	578	19	FO	23	-
FR	5,640	2	GB	5,441	2246
HR	58	-	HU	124	-
IE	1,502	3	IS	2	-
IT	36	-	LT	183	-
LU	61	-	LV	50	-
NL	1,307	524	NO	903	2
PL	1,763	-	RO	415	-
RS	171	-	SE	4,575	79
SI	2	-	SK	5	-
UA	244	-			

The methods developed in the DTU/NCKF project will be used for WIMBY to produce a data set, as complete as possible, of Wind turbine locations and characteristics for the entire Europe. Parameters from open data sources (such as location and hub height) will be shared with the consortium and the public. Parameters coming from licensed databases can only be shared under the conditions of the licenses. For example, The WindPower data [21] will only be available to other partners already holding a paid license.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

4.1 Conclusions

This report described the meteorological and wind energy data required for the Wind Power tool and other partners' model development and calculations for the WIMBY project. Most of the data comes from previous projects but has been enhanced and expanded specifically for use in WIMBY.

The main tasks completed during this period were:

- Four additional years of simulations for the NEWA mesoscale time series data were run.
- The NEWA time series dataset was re-chunked and saved as a Zarr archive to improve access speed when requesting long periods for a small area.
- A new dataset to characterize the temporal variation of the wind was created using the ERA5 reanalysis and a ratio between the mean GWA2 and ERA5 wind speeds at 100m AGL.

4.2 Future Work

Several tasks are to be completed in the next six months:

- The NaN values in the NEWA time series data will be filled using nearest neighbor interpolation in time.
- The updated Zarr archive will be exposed through an API with the fix for the missing data.
- The updated NEWA microscale run will be completed.
- The data from the GASP model will be documented and shared.
- An updated correction factor map for the ERA5 data will be created based on the NEWA microscale run.
- The wind turbine database will be updated to cover all Europe and include additional wind turbine characteristics that will be distributed according to the partner's licenses.

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